

Website concept and prototype ready

Deliverable 10.1

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Type of deliverable

R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination level

PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Introduction	4
3. Website features	5
3.1 Look and feel	5
3.2 Responsive design.....	6
3.3 News archiving.....	6
4. Current website contents	6
4.1 Homepage - www.oh-fine.eu	6
4.2 About - www.oh-fine.eu/about	6
4.3 Knowledge Centre - www.oh-fine.eu/knowledge-center	7
4.4 Communication - www.oh-fine.eu/communications	8
4.5 Contact - www.oh-fine.eu/contact.....	9
4.6 Site information	9
4.7 Privacy policy	9
5. Content to be added to the website	9
5.1 ICT Tool	9
5.2 Regional hubs	9
5.3 Field trials.....	9
5.4 Related projects	10
6. Future actions to further develop the OH-FINE website	10

List of Figures

Figure 1: The OH-FINE homepage	5
Figure 2: The OH-FINE work package overview page	7
Figure 3. The Organic Farm Knowledge subpage on the OH-FINE website.....	8

1. Executive Summary

The Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe (OH-FINE) project website has been successfully developed as the main information hub for the project. Managed by FiBL Switzerland in collaboration with SEAE and project partners, the website serves as a key dissemination tool for farmers, researchers, advisors and the public. The platform provides essential project details, news, publications, events and other resources to support sustainable organic agriculture.

Launched in December 2024, the website (www.oh-fine.eu) features a responsive design, news archive and structured sections describing the project. A dedicated knowledge centre will feature practical materials and research findings.

Future enhancements will include translations into different languages, and additional pages on the ICT tool, regional hubs, field trials and related projects. Ongoing content updates, partner engagement and structured information sharing will ensure that the platform remains dynamic and relevant. The website will evolve throughout the project lifecycle to support stakeholder engagement and long-term impact.

2. Introduction

The OH-FINE project website was developed and is managed by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), with content contributions supported by the project coordinator CSIC and all other project partners.

The website serves as the primary information hub for the project, offering comprehensive details about the project and its outcomes. It is designed for a variety of audiences, including farmers, advisors, researchers, and the general public. As a vital communication and dissemination tool, the website provides relevant information and practical materials to support the project's goals.

The OH-FINE website will be continuously updated and enhanced throughout the project's duration. In alignment with Grant Agreement No. 101183127, the website will include the following key information and resources:

- Project information
- News
- Publications
- Dissemination material
- Project workshops
- Conferences and other events
- Communication and promotional material
- Number of partners
- Countries represented in the project
- Horizon call number
- Funding organizations
- Description of the work packages
- Description of the partner organizations

- Map to visualize the geographic distribution of the project partners

The registered domain name for the project website is www.oh-fine.eu. The domain name was selected based on the following criteria:

- Ensuring it is easily recognizable and closely associated with the project name and research area.
- Maintaining consistency with the branding of other project-related social media platforms, including LinkedIn, YouTube, and Facebook.

The project website, www.oh-fine.eu, was launched in December 2024 and currently provides essential information about the project.

The project coordinator, along with SEAE, the partner responsible for communication, reviewed the prototype of the website and provided feedback and suggestions regarding its structure and content. Several of these suggestions have already been implemented.

The main language of the project website is English. Currently, the OH-FINE website is only available in English. In the coming months, it will be translated into the languages of all project partner countries. AI-generated translations will be used and checked by partners where deemed relevant.

The following sections outline the current status of the website and provide an overview of planned future developments.

3. Website features

3.1 Look and feel

The OH-FINE logo is prominently displayed in the upper-left corner of the website, serving as a key visual element. The website's colour scheme, developed by FiBL's graphic design team, features a range of green shades inspired by the OH-FINE logo. These colour variations are strategically applied to distinguish different sections of the site. The overall layout and design align seamlessly with the visual identity of the OH-FINE project, ensuring consistency and brand recognition.

Figure 1: The OH-FINE homepage

3.2 Responsive design

The OH-FINE website has been designed as a fully responsive platform, ensuring optimal viewing and usability across various screen sizes and web browsers. Specifically, the website is mobile-friendly, allowing seamless access and navigation on smartphones and other devices. Its development prioritizes delivering an exceptional user experience on any device, adapting effortlessly to meet diverse user needs.

3.3 News archiving

The project website contains a functionality for automatically archiving news.

4. Current website contents

4.1 Homepage - www.oh-fine.eu

The homepage contains:

- A short introduction to the OH-FINE project
- OH-FINE news
- The social media icons with links to the OH-FINE social media accounts
- An information box about the OH-FINE project, including details on funding, grant agreement number, coordinator information, duration of the project, and a link to Cordis
- The contact information of the project coordinator
- Project events and outreach activities by partners will be announced directly on the homepage and through the project's social media accounts.

Future action: Keep the OH-FINE website alive with news, and social media posts, and add new pictures from OH-FINE events.

4.2 About - www.oh-fine.eu/about

The "About" page on the OH-FINE website provides information about the project, its context and approach, and outlines its objectives.

The page currently includes three subpages with information about the work packages, partners and details on project funding.

4.2.1 Work packages

The "Work Packages" page outlines the overall concept of the work packages. There is a subpage for each work package, which lists the individual tasks, and includes the contact information for each work package leader.

Figure 2: The OH-FINE work package overview page

4.2.2 Partners

The main section of the "Partners" page features a group photo from the kick-off meeting in Madrid and a map illustrating the geographic distribution of the project partners.

There is a subpage for each partner, which offers a brief description of the partner and their roles in the project. It also includes links to each partner's website, their logo, and the contact information of individuals involved in the project.

Future action: Remind partners to check partner descriptions annually and send updates if needed.

4.2.3 Funding

The "Funding" page presents the funding program and funding bodies, along with links to their respective websites.

4.3 Knowledge Centre - www.oh-fine.eu/knowledge-center

The "Knowledge Centre" page will provide access to all practice materials, publications, deliverables, and videos.

Future action: Fill the knowledge centre page with information and knowledge as the project continues. Organise the content according to relevant categories.

4.3.1 Organic Farm Knowledge

The subpage will feature a description of the Organic Farm Knowledge website, with a link provided. All dissemination materials produced throughout the OH-FINE project will

be uploaded to this platform, ensuring continued access even after the project's completion.

Figure 3. The Organic Farm Knowledge subpage on the OH-FINE website

Future action: Create an OH-FINE profile on the Organic Farm Knowledge Platform and upload OH-FINE practical materials.

4.4 Communication - www.oh-fine.eu/communications

The “Communication” page provides links to three categories of communication: News, events and social media.

4.4.1 News

The subpage “News” contains all the news published on the OH-FINE website. The news items are then archived and remain accessible on the website.

Future action: Upload news items regularly.

4.4.2 Events

All information on upcoming and past events such as fora, workshops, cross-visits, and field demonstrations can be found on the “Events” subpage.

Future action: Upload all information on the various events planned during the project period. The information will be provided by all project partners.

4.4.3 Social media

The “Social Media” subpage contains links to the social media channels that are already active. It will be updated as more channels are implemented.

Future action: Implement additional social media channels in addition to LinkedIn and YouTube.

4.5 Contact - www.oh-fine.eu/contact

The “Contact” page shows the project coordinator’s contact details and the contacts for the website.

4.6 Site information

The "Site Information" page is located in the footer of the project website. This page contains the site information, publisher, copyright, liability, disclaimer, and acknowledgment of the European Union and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), as well as image credits.

4.7 Privacy policy

The “privacy policy” page can also be found in the footer of the OH-FINE website. On the right, the content of this page is listed.

5. Content to be added to the website

In addition to updating the pages mentioned above, the need for additional pages has already been identified. These pages will be added soon.

5.1 ICT Tool

On the "ICT Tool" page, there will be a short description of the tool and a link to the Decision Support System ICT Tool once the tool is created and ready to use. This page will be active as soon as the tool exists.

Future action: Make the “ICT page” visible and link the page to the DSS ICT Tool as soon as available.

5.2 Regional hubs

The “Regional Hubs” page will introduce each regional hub.

Future action: Coordinate with work package 3 to finalise the “Regional hubs” page concept and fill it with the relevant information about each hub.

5.3 Field trials

The “Field Trials” page will describe the field trials, their duration, location, objectives, problems, and solutions. It will be accompanied by pictures and infographics, if available,

and contact details of the field trial leader. A template has been created and circulated among field trials to collect the necessary information.

Future action: coordinate with work package 7 to fill the “Field trials” page and periodically update the field trial information.

5.4 Related projects

The “Related projects” page will list projects we are working with, providing a brief description of each and including the contact information for the project coordinators.

Future action: Fill the “Related projects” page with information about related projects.

6. Future actions to further develop the OH-FINE website

The following actions are expected to be implemented on this website in the near future or on a periodic basis. As new needs arise, the necessary steps will be taken.

- Translate the OH-FINE website into all partner languages
- Keep the OH-FINE website alive with news, and social media posts, and add new pictures from OH-FINE events.
- Remind partners to check partner descriptions annually and send updates if needed.
- Fill the knowledge centre page with information and knowledge as the project continues. Organise the content according to relevant categories.
- Create OH-FINE profile on the Organic Farm Knowledge Platform and upload OH-FINE practical materials.
- Upload news items regularly.
- Upload all information on the various events planned during the project period. The information will be provided by all project partners.
- Implement additional social media channels in addition to LinkedIn and YouTube.
- Make the “ICT page” visible and link the page to the DSS ICT Tool as soon as available.
- Coordinate with work package 3 to finalise the “Regional hubs” page concept and fill it with the relevant information about each hub
- Coordinate with work package 7 to fill the “Field trials” page and periodically update the field trial information.
- Fill the “Related projects” page with information about related projects.